

The first records of *Promyialges italicus* and *Myialges anchora* (Acariformes: Epidermoptidae) in Slovakia with new hosts

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Abstract: Epidermoptidae (Acariformes: Astigmata) are permanent ectoparasites of birds; representatives of some genera have evolved phoretic associations with louse flies (Hippoboscidae). Moreover, mites of some genera hyperparasitise their phoretic carriers, using them for oviposition and in some cases for feeding. In the course of research focused on bird migrations and avian ectoparasites carried out in Eastern Slovakia in 2022 and 2023, we collected 76 hippoboscid flies of 7 species from 71 birds of 20 species; of these flies, 6 individuals (8 %) were parasitised by epidermoptid mites. *Promyialges italicus* Faradonbeh et al., 2019 was found on the wings of *Ornithomya avicularia* (Linnaeus, 1758) and *O. biloba* Dufour, 1827, both from barn swallow, *Hirundo rustica* Linnaeus, 1758. *Myialges anchora* Sergent & Trouessart, 1907 was found on the abdomens of louse flies of three species: *Ornithoica turdi* (Olivier in Latreille, 1811), *Ornithomya fringillina* Curtis, 1836, and *O. avicularia* (Linnaeus, 1758) from the three different avian hosts: *Lanius collurio* Linnaeus, 1758, *Acrocephalus arundinaceus* (Linnaeus, 1758), and *Turdus merula* Linnaeus, 1758, respectively. *Promyialges italicus* has been recorded on a host other than *Pseudolynchia canariensis* (Macquart in Webb & Berthelot, 1839) for the first time. Neither species of this mite has been reported in Slovakia.

Keywords: Diptera, Hippoboscidae, mites, Passeriformes, phoresis

Introduction

The family Epidermoptidae (Acariformes: Astigmata) comprises species that are normally parasitic on the skin of the birds (Houck, 1993; Krantz & Walter, 2009; Yamauchi & Kuroki, 2009). They are specialised to live in the upper layers of the host skin and in feather follicles, where they burrow in the epidermis (Houck, 1993; Krantz & Walter, 2009). Members of the family can be significantly pathogenic, they can cause dermatitis and lesions on different body parts, around the bill and on the head (e.g. Fain, 1962, 1965; Matyukhin et al., 2021; Yatsuk & Matyukhin, 2021; Matyukhin & Yatsuk, 2022), leg

deformities and lameness, and even severe dermatitis, leading to mortality of nestlings (Gilardi et al., 2002); therefore, this group of mites is of significant epidemiological importance.

A simple phoretic relationships can be observed in the genus *Microlichus* (Epidermoptinae): gravid females, dwelling on their avian hosts, attach to ectoparasitic hippoboscid flies (Diptera: Hippoboscidae) and use them for only for dispersal to another avian hosts (Mironov et al., 2005; Goater et al., 2018). Epidermoptid mites of the subfamily Myialginae – *Archemyialges*, *Hemimyialges*, *Myialges*, and *Promyialges* – a peculiar shift related to a mites' life history evolved. When mite females

are on their phoretic carriers, they oviposit (Fain, 1965; Houck, 1993; Gouter et al., 2018). Females can attach even to feather lice that themselves can phoretically attach to louse flies (Gouter et al., 2018). As insect ectoparasites move from one avian host to another, and juvenile mites hatching from these eggs go onto new bird hosts. This form of phoresy by highly vagile arthropods dramatically increases mites' dispersal capacity among diverse avian hosts (Bequaert, 1953; Evans et al., 1963; Hill et al., 1967; Goater et al., 2018). A low specificity of hippoboscids to their avian hosts enables epidermoptids to disperse over a wide spectrum of hosts; therefore, their avian host specificity is extremely weak, and the same mite species may parasitise birds belonging to different orders (Krantz & Walter, 2009).

Upon hatching, immature myialgine mites leave the fly to colonise the skin or feather bases of a new avian host (Goater et al., 2018). Phoretic hosts provide also the additional benefit for myialgines as a food source – mite females feed on their hemolymph (Mironov et al., 2005; Walter & Proctor, 2013). Thus, they are hyperparasites. Nymphs and male mites remain on the avian host, while for myialgine females, this hyperparasitic behaviour seems to be facultative (Whiteman et al., 2006; Krantz & Walter, 2009).

Although Epidermoptidae are of admittedly high parasitological and veterinary importance, complex ecological interactions among their avian and hippoboscid hosts stay rather understudied (Whiteman et al., 2006; Goater et al., 2018). Epidermoptids were only anecdotally recorded from Slovakia. Jamriška et al. (2011) published the hyperparasitic mite *Promyialges uncus* (Vitzthum, 1934) from *Ornithomya avicularia* (Linnaeus, 1758) from nestlings of *Turdus merula* Linnaeus, 1758 and *Hirundo rustica* Linnaeus, 1758. Oboňa et al. (2019) published a finding of unidentified epidermoptid mites on *Ornithomya avicularia* from *Pyrrhula pyrrhula* (Linnaeus, 1758). The present study aims to publish new records of Epidermoptidae from Slovakia with information on their host associations with both avian and hippoboscid flies.

Material and methods

The louse flies were collected from birds in East Slovakia in 2022 and 2023 by professional ringers

during the research of bird migration and avian ectoparasites, using mist-netting. A total of 2273 birds of 54 species were investigated for the presence of hippoboscid flies (for more details, see Mlynárová et al. (2024) for the year 2022, and Krišovský et al. (2024) for the year 2023).

All collected hippoboscid flies were placed in Eppendorf tubes, filled with 96 % ethanol, and subsequently identified using a determination key by Oboňa et al. (2022). The infected louse flies with mites were then examined in detail, and photographed; mites were identified according to Oudemans (1935), Fain (1965), and Faradonbeh et al. (2019). The material is deposited in the slides and ethanol in the Laboratory and Museum of Evolutionary Ecology, Department of Ecology, University of Prešov (LMEE PO).

Descriptive statistics were computed using Quantitative Parasitology on the Web (QPWeb), with 95 % confidence intervals (Sterne method for prevalence) (Reiczigel et al., 2019).

Results and discussion

Of 76 hippoboscid flies of seven species parasitising 71 birds of 20 species (Krišovský et al., 2024; Mlynárová et al., 2024), 6 flies (8 %) were parasitised by epidermoptid mites (see also Table 1 – descriptive statistics).

Faunistic records

Myialges anchora Sergent & Trouessart, 1907 (Fig. 1)

Hippoboscid host: *Ornithoica turdi* (Olivier in Latreille, 1811), N = 1, 1 infected fly. 1 female mite with eggs on the fly's abdomen.

Locality: Drienovec, 48°36'54.5"N 20°54'54.7"E, date: 23.8.2022. Avian host: *Lanius collurio* Linnaeus, 1758 (Bird ring: N24615).

Hippoboscid host: *Ornithomya fringillina* Curtis, 1836, N = 2, infected 1 fly, 9 female mites on abdomen.

Locality: Uzovský Šalgov, 49°05'34.8"N 21°04'00.2"E, date: 17.8.2023. Avian host: *Acrocephalus arundinaceus* (Linnaeus, 1758) (N24939).

Fig. 1. Female mite, *Myialges anchora* Sergent & Trouessart, 1907, from the hippoboscid fly (*Ornithoica turdi* (Olivier in Latreille, 1811)) collected from *Lanius collurio* Linnaeus, 1758 in eastern Slovakia. A. Female mite with a cluster of eggs attached to the posterior segment of fly. B. Detail of female mite with a cluster of eggs. C. Female mite.

Hippoboscid host: *Ornithomya avicularia*, N = 8, infected 1 fly, 1 female mite on abdomen.

Locality: Uzovský Šalgov, 49°05'34.8"N 21°04'00.3"E, date: 10.8.2023. Avian host: *Turdus merula* (L42985).

Myialges anchora is a relatively common hyperparasitic mite known from the Afrotropical, Palearctic, Nearctic, Neotropical and Oriental regions (Theodor, 1975). This mite is mostly known from *Pseudolynchia canariensis* (Macquart in Webb & Berthelot, 1839) (e.g. Sergent & Trouessart, 1907; Oudemans, 1935; Furman & Tarshis, 1953; Hiregaudar, 1956; Evans et al., 1963; Macchioni et al., 2005; Valim & Gazêta, 2007; Marcelino et al., 2009; da Cunha Amaral et al., 2013; Rahimi et al., 2017; Faradonbeh et al., 2019), in all cases from domestic pigeons *Columba livia* Gmelin, 1789. This mite is also known from the other hippoboscid hosts: *Ornithoica confluenta* (Say, 1823) (Ferris, 1928), *O. philippinensis* Ferris, 1927

(Thompson, 1936), and *Icosta (Ornithoponus) hirsuta* (Ferris, 1927) (Maa, 1969).

Myialges anchora has been recorded from avian hosts of orders Columbiformes, Falconiformes, Galliformes, Piciformes, and Strigiformes (Mironov et al., 2010), this is the first record from the order Passeriformes.

This paper presents the first record of *M. anchora* for the fauna of Slovakia.

Promyialges italicus Faradonbeh et al., 2019 (Fig. 2)

Hippoboscid host: *Ornithomya avicularia*.

(1) N = 19, 1 infected fly, 2 adult females with eggs on wing.

Locality (1): Hromoš, Poprad River, 49°15'50.8"N 20°48'29.2"E, 7.07.2022. Avian host: *Hirundo rustica* Linnaeus, 1758 (U 87734).

Fig. 2. Female mite, *Promyialges italicus* Faradonbeh et al. 2019, from the hippoboscid fly (*Ornithomya avicularia* (Linnaeus, 1758)) collected from *Hirundo rustica* Linnaeus, 1758 in eastern Slovakia. A. Two female's mites with a clusters of eggs attached under the wing of fly. B. Detail of female's mites with a cluster of eggs, view from the underside of the wing. C. Female mite with a cluster of eggs. D. Female mite.

(2) N = 8, 1 infected fly, 1 adult female with eggs on each wing (together 2).

Locality (2): Uzovský Šalgov, 49°05'34.8"N 21°04'00.4"E, 8.08.2023. Avian host: *H. rustica* (no ring).

Hippoboscid host: *Ornithomya biloba* Dufour, 1827, N = 10, 1 infected fly, 1 adult female with eggs on wing.

Locality data: Uzovský Šalgov, 49°05'34.8"N 21°04'00.2"E, 20.08.2023. Avian host *H. rustica* (U106924).

Promyialges italicus was described by Faradonbeh et al. (2019) from the wings of a louse fly *Pseudolynchia canariensis* from the domestic pigeon in Italy. Matyukhin & Yatsuk (2022) recorded this species from the same hippoboscid and avian hosts from Russia.

To our knowledge, this is the third finding of the mite species, and at the same time the record of a new hippoboscid host.

The family Epidermoptidae is divided into ten genera (namely: *Archemyialges*, *Congocoptes*, *Epi-*

Table 1. Host associations and parasitological data of epidermoptid mites in Slovakia.

Mite	Hippoboscid host	Avian host	No of flies	No of infected flies	Prevalence % (Sterne's confidence interval)	Mean intensity
<i>Myialges anchora</i>	<i>Ornithoica turdi</i>	<i>Lanius collurio</i>	1	1	100 (50–100)	1
	<i>Ornithomya fringillina</i>	<i>Acrocephalus arundinaceus</i>	2	1	50 (2.5–97.5)	9
	<i>Ornithomya avicularia</i>	<i>Turdus merula</i>	8	1	12.5 (0.6–50)	1
<i>Promyialges italicus</i>	<i>Ornithomya avicularia</i>	<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	27	2	7.4 (1.3–23.7)	2
	<i>Ornithomya biloba</i>		10	1	10 (0.5–44.7)	1

dermoptes, *Hemimyialges*, *Microlichus*, *Myialges*, *Otocoptoides*, *Pelicanoptes*, *Promyialges* and *Rallepidermoptes*) (IRMNG 2021). Recently, two genera and three species are known from Slovakia.

As Goater et al. (2018) noticed, despite complex hyperparasitic networks that span multiple trophic levels have been described for example for parasitoid–host interactions or microparasites of metazoan and protist parasites, almost nothing is known regarding the nature of the key ecological and physiological interactions that occur between birds, their hippoboscid flies (and/or Phthiraptera), and their hyperparasitic mites. In the complex interactions we have studied in Slovakia, individual birds are likely to be hosts for both the hippoboscids and its parasitic mites. However, we did not investigate the presence of epidermoptid mites directly on their avian hosts, only indirectly, via their phoretic dipteran carriers collected from birds. For a better understanding of host, parasite, and hyperparasite community ecology and its epidemiological implications, more detailed studies of alpha and gamma diversity of all trophic levels and in different geographic regions are highly needed.

Acknowledgements

We thank the editor and all anonymous reviewers for their valuable and constructive comments on the first version of the manuscript. This work was supported by the Slovak Research and Development Agency under contract No. APVV-22-0440, by the Ministry of

Education, Research, Development and Youth of the Slovak Republic VEGA-1/0876/21, and by the Grant Agency for Doctoral Students and Young Researchers of the University of Prešov.

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